

1 *Supplementary Material for* 2 **Lightweight Diagramming for Lightweight Formal** 3 **Methods:** 4 **A Grounded Language Design**

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13 **1 What Is Included In This Supplement**

14 This supplement includes the following files:

- 15 1. `supplement.pdf`: This document.
 - 16 2. `cnd.tar` : A tarball containing the CnD visualization tool. Instructions on how to load and
17 run the tool are provided in section 3.1.
 - 18 3. The `supp-cnd-and-data` directory, that contains `.cnd` layout files and corresponding alloy
19 instance (`.xml`) files for each scenario visualized in the paper.
 - 20 4. The `survey-instruments` directory, containing the following `.qsf` files:
 - 21 a. `Instance_Understanding.qsf`
 - 22 b. `Instance_Understanding_Icons.qsf`
 - 23 c. `BadInstance_Understanding.qsf`
- 24 Instructions on how to load these files are provided in section 2.

25 CnD is embedded in an open-source tool that serves as a substitute visualizer for Alloy and
26 Forge. This supplement presents instructions on how to install and run the version of CnD
27 presented in the accompanying paper.¹

28 An interested reader can also find the latest version of CnD at [https://github.com/sidprasad/](https://github.com/sidprasad/copeanddrag/)
29 [copeanddrag/](https://sidprasad.github.io/copeanddrag/) with up to date documentation at <https://sidprasad.github.io/copeanddrag/>.

30 **2 Study Instruments**

31 The surveys in the paper's section 5.2 are provided in the Qualtrics `.qsf` format. A QSF file can
32 be imported into Qualtrics as detailed here:

33 [https://www.qualtrics.com/support/survey-platform/survey-module/survey-tools/](https://www.qualtrics.com/support/survey-platform/survey-module/survey-tools/import-and-export-surveys/)
34 [import-and-export-surveys/](https://www.qualtrics.com/support/survey-platform/survey-module/survey-tools/import-and-export-surveys/)

¹ Source code available at <https://github.com/sidprasad/copeanddrag/tree/ecoop-2025>.

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35 **3 Paper Visualizations**

36 To fully evaluate the content of the accompanying paper, the reader may wish to look closely at
37 several visualizations. These visualizations are provided as both as interactive CnD visualizations
38 (section 3.1) and as higher-resolution images (section 3.2).

39 **3.1 Interactive Visualizations**

40 The primary claim in the paper is that CnD is able to produce a variety of interactive, constraint-
41 based visualizations. To access interactive CnD visualizations, install Docker.

42 You can then access visualizations by running

43 `docker image load -i cnd.tar`

44 and then

45 `docker run --rm -it -p 3000:3000 cnd:latest`

46 This makes CnD available at `http://localhost:3000`. All paper examples are available at

47 `http://localhost:3000/example`

48 and specific examples can be accessed at

49 `http://localhost:3000/example/<example_name>`

50 For instance, the `ab` visualization is available at `http://localhost:3000/example/ab`.

51 Due to the nature of WebCola and D3 layout algorithms, the interactive visualizations may
52 differ slightly from the images in the paper (e.g., link lengths may be larger or smaller). Crucially,
53 however, every produced visualization is guaranteed to enforce the constraints in the accompanying
54 CnD spec. The *Diagram Compactness* slider in the bottom left of the CnD controls panel can be
55 used to adjust link lengths and node spacing.

56 The *Apply Layout* button on the top-right can be used to reapply the layout. We encourage
57 the reader to play with the layout parameters to see how they affect the visualization.

58 **3.2 Full Diagrams**

(a) Alloy Default Visualizer: This visualization obscures the spatial relationship between **Light3** and **Light0**. The two lights are directly adjacent, with **Light3** to the right of **Light0**.

(b) CnD visualization using a cyclic constraint on the left field.

```
constraints:
- cyclic:
  field: left
  direction: clockwise
```

(c) CnD spec

■ **Figure 1** **ring-lights** Alloy Default Visualizer and CnD visualizations of a light-switching puzzle instance involving 5 lights in a ring from the Forge examples repository. Lights that are lit are colored red, while unlit lights are colored grey.

(a) Alloy Default Visualizer: By laying out **left** children to the right and **right** children to the left, this visualization lends itself to spatial Stroop effects.

(b) CnD visualization using orientation constraints. All nodes along the **left** field are laid below and to the left of their parent node, while nodes along the **right** field are placed to the right and below their parent node.

```

constraints:
- orientation:
  field: left
  directions: [below, left]
- orientation:
  field: right
  directions: [below, right]
directives:
- attribute: { field: key }
- flag: hideDisconnected
  
```

(c) CnD spec

■ Figure 2 [bt](#) Alloy Default Visualizer and CnD visualizations of a binary tree.

(a) Alloy Default Visualizer: This visualization does not spatially group animals by shore, making it harder to determine if the spec is valid.

(b) CnD visualization using a grouping constraint on the `animals` field. All animals are grouped together by the shore they are on.

```
constraints:
  - group:
      field: animals
      target: domain
```

(c) CnD spec

■ **Figure 3** [rc](#) Alloy Default Visualizer and CnD representations of a river-crossing puzzle instance, where a valid spec must ensure that wolves never outnumber goats on either shore.


```

constraints :
- orientation :
  field: parent
  directions: [above]
- group :
  field: entries
  target: domain
- orientation :
  field: entries
  directions: [directlyRight]
directives :
- attribute :
  field: name
- attribute :
  field: contents
- flag: hideDisconnected
    
```

(c) CnD spec

■ **Figure 4** An instance of the Filesystem specification visualized by the Alloy Default Visualizer and using CnD.

(a) Alloy Default Visualizer

(b) ring-orientation CnD diagram.

```

constraints:
- cyclic:
    field: rightNeighbor
    direction: counterclockwise
- cyclic:
    field: ring
    direction: clockwise
directives:
- flag: hideDisconnected
- attribute:
    field: dir
- attribute:
    field: S
- attribute:
    field: T
- projection:
    sig: this/Tick
    
```

(c) CnD spec

Figure 5 An instance of the Ring Orientation specification visualized by the Alloy Default Visualizer and using CnD.

(a) Alloy Default Visualizer diagram .

(b) `phil-inv` CnD diagram.

```

constraints:
  - cyclic : {field: leftPhil}
  - attribute: {field: rightPhil, direction: counterclockwise}
directives:
  - projection : {sig: this/State}
  - projection: {sig: so/Ord}
  - projection: {sig: po/Ord}
  - attribute: {field: Next}
  - flag: hideDisconnectedBuiltIns
  - icon:
      sig: this/Fork
      icon:
        path: 'img/fork.png'
        height: 50
        width: 50
  - icon:
      sig: this/Philosopher
      icon:
        path: 'img/person.png'
        height: 50
        width: 50
    
```

(c) CnD spec

■ **Figure 6** Outputs for a bad instance of a dining-philosophers spec. The instance has 6 forks but only 5 philosophers.

(a) Alloy Default Visualizer.

(b) chord CnD diagram.

```

constraints:
- group:
  field: active
  target: domain
- group:
  field: closest_preceding_finger
- group:
  field: find_predecessor
- group:
  field: find_successor
- orientation:
  field: prev
  directions:
  - directlyLeft
directives:
- flag: hideDisconnected
- attribute:
  field: id

```

(c) CnD spec.

■ **Figure 7** An instance of the Chord specification visualized by the Alloy Default Visualizer and using CnD.

(a) **fruit** Fruit visualization, with default text nodes.

(b) **fruit-icons** Fruit visualization with icons.

■ **Figure 8** Fruit visualizations

(a) `ttt` CnD diagram of the valid Tic-Tac-Toe board.

(b) `ttt-inv` CnD diagram of the invalid Tic-Tac-Toe board.

(c) Alloy Default Visualizer diagram of the valid Tic-Tac-Toe board.

(d) Alloy Default Visualizer visualization of the invalid Tic-Tac-Toe board.

■ **Figure 9** The diagrams of valid and invalid Tic-Tac-Toe boards, as described in CnD paper table 2.

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(a) `face` CnD diagram of the valid face instance.

(b) `face-inv` CnD diagram of the invalid face instance.

(c) Alloy Default Visualizer diagram of the valid face instance.

(d) Alloy Default Visualizer diagram of the invalid face instance.

■ **Figure 10** Diagrams of valid and invalid face instances, as described in CnD paper table 2.

4 Performance Data

The paper’s Section 5.3 makes claims about the performance of the CnD system when generating diagrams, emphasizing that the system generates diagrams within roughly 1 second at most. Table 1 provides the average time taken for each example diagram to be laid out by CnD. Each diagram was laid out 50 times on a machine with 16GB of memory, powered by a 2.30 GHz processor (AMD Ryzen 7).

Table 1 Time taken for Alloy instances to be laid out by CnD.

Scenario	Constraint Solving		Graph Layout		Total	
	Mean	S.D.	Mean	S.D.	Mean	S.D.
ab	12.13 ms	3.07 ms	395.20 ms	11.22 ms	407.33 ms	11.46 ms
bt-dag	16.56 ms	20.38 ms	N/A	N/A	16.56 ms	20.38 ms
bt	19.24 ms	10.29 ms	325.93 ms	9.75 ms	345.17 ms	13.71 ms
cards	31.37 ms	7.73 ms	469.67 ms	11.50 ms	501.05 ms	14.23 ms
chord	29.60 ms	10.22 ms	955.25 ms	13.42 ms	984.85 ms	16.01 ms
face-inv	29.67 ms	7.72 ms	1032.47 ms	11.00 ms	1062.14 ms	13.53 ms
face	27.43 ms	8.45 ms	1007.28 ms	9.06 ms	1034.71 ms	12.03 ms
filesystem	30.30 ms	11.29 ms	456.80 ms	15.47 ms	487.10 ms	21.46 ms
fruit-icons	32.55 ms	10.29 ms	252.08 ms	14.03 ms	284.62 ms	19.32 ms
fruit	33.23 ms	9.59 ms	289.38 ms	268.37 ms	322.61 ms	268.90 ms
grid	26.68 ms	8.63 ms	446.16 ms	14.05 ms	472.84 ms	17.64 ms
phil-inv	44.63 ms	12.83 ms	457.94 ms	12.15 ms	502.57 ms	18.08 ms
phil	43.34 ms	13.34 ms	441.04 ms	10.46 ms	484.39 ms	17.50 ms
rc	47.96 ms	12.19 ms	193.81 ms	18.69 ms	241.77 ms	21.21 ms
ring-lights	43.54 ms	15.35 ms	492.47 ms	12.47 ms	536.02 ms	20.12 ms
ring-orientation	32.63 ms	9.96 ms	387.70 ms	12.42 ms	420.33 ms	17.88 ms
subway	22.98 ms	7.47 ms	411.93 ms	15.57 ms	434.89 ms	18.62 ms
ttt-inv	25.30 ms	8.35 ms	431.58 ms	13.10 ms	456.88 ms	18.35 ms
ttt	26.02 ms	8.51 ms	399.30 ms	11.78 ms	425.04 ms	15.47 ms
undirected-tree	19.27 ms	5.88 ms	84.46 ms	9.84 ms	103.76 ms	12.25 ms

The reader can test the performance of CnD in the Docker container by running the following command:

```
docker run --rm -it cnd:latest --benchmark <ex_name> <times>
```

where `<ex_name>` is the name of the example to test, and `<times>` is the number of times the example should be run. For instance, to test the `bt` example over 10 runs, run:

```
docker run --rm -it cnd:latest --benchmark bt 10
```

To test *all* examples, run:

```
docker run --rm -it cnd:latest --benchmark --all <times>
```

While performance may differ depending on machine and docker resources, we believe that diagrams will be generated in roughly one second or less for all examples.